

On the nature of solvothermally synthesized carbon nanodots

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Due to their facile synthesis, biocompatibility, high apparent photoluminescence (PL) quantum yield and applications in photocatalysis, sensing and biomarkers carbon nanodots (CNDs) have been investigated intensively in recent years. Solvothermal synthesis of CNDs, however, results in complex mixtures of CNDs with molecular byproducts and some of the reported properties of CNDs are rather due to the latter. Here, we present an extensive analysis of two types of solvothermal CNDs synthesized from (a) citric acid and ethylenediamine (B-CNDs) and (b) *p*-phenylenediamine (R-CNDs). Study of the fractions separated by dialysis confirms the overwhelming formation of molecular fluorophores and non-conjugated small molecules. PL, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) confirm the presence of the fluorophores in the retentate fraction even after prolonged dialysis. By means of liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (UPLC-ESI-Q-TOF-MS/MS) we unequivocally identify some of the molecules. AFM and HR-TEM reveals graphitic cores with a diameter of approximately 3 nm which are further studied by grazing incidence wide angle X-ray scattering (GI-WAXS) and surface-enhanced micro-Raman spectroscopy (SERS). In the case of B-CNDs, the formation of photoproducts was observed, which readily explains differences in the optical properties of dialysate and retentate fractions. Surprisingly, for both types of CNDs the carbon dots formed and their expected sp^2 domains are not detected at all by PL, PL excitation, UV-Vis spectroscopy or fluorescence correlation spectroscopy. On the other hand, a significant photophysical effect of the CNDs, as opposed to the molecular byproducts, is observed in view of singlet oxygen generation.

Introduction

Solvothermally synthesized carbon nanodots (CNDs) have received tremendous attention because of their significant advantages in terms of their easy, cheap and green metal-free synthesis, excellent biocompatibility, low cytotoxicity and apparent outstanding photophysical properties, such as high fluorescence quantum yield and high photostability.¹⁻⁸ Such desirable combination of properties suggests opportunities for replacing conventional fluorescent materials in various fields of applications, ranging from optoelectronics, photovoltaics or photocatalysis to biomedicine.⁹⁻²⁰ This interest has led to an almost exponential growth in the number of scientific articles published on the subject, but, on the other hand, this rapid

pace has been accompanied by a host of misconceptions that have hindered the elucidation of the true nature of carbon dots. The characterization of the structure and photophysics of solvothermally synthesized CNDs is complicated by the fact that it is masked by the presence of molecular and oligomeric products partially attached to the CNDs. For this reason, it is essential to carefully purify the synthesized materials, to know all the major reaction products generated during the synthesis and to compare the properties of the fractions separated in the purification step.^{21,22} Related to this problem, there is still controversy about the photophysical properties of CNDs. Part of the recent studies ascribe the fluorescence of one of the CNDs studied in the present work actually to conjugated small molecules, such as IPCA (imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-7-carboxylic acid, 1,2,3,5-tetrahydro-5oxo),²³ or similar structures.²⁴⁻²⁷ Recent reports on fluorescence or phosphorescence from non-conjugated polymer dots²⁸⁻³² also do not appear to fully exclude the presence of small conjugated molecules as the origin of those emissions. In line with the results presented below mass spectrometry of the synthesized products at m/z \approx 1500,

extensive dialysis and comparison of the PL of dialysate and retentate, respectively, are indispensable for this purpose. In general, the published work still does not sufficiently characterize the complex products that arise from solvothermal synthesis of CNDs. The present work attempts to contribute to this task. To this end we have synthesized solvothermal CNDs (a) from citric acid and ethylenediamine as sources of carbon and nitrogen, respectively (blue carbon dots, B-CNDs), one of the most frequently studied types of solvothermal carbon dots, and (b) from *p*-phenylenediamine as precursors (red carbon dots, R-CNDs).^{33–35}

Results and discussion

Synthetic procedures of B-CNDs

Different hydrothermal treatments of citric acid and ethylenediamine were explored to synthesize CNDs. The definitive hydrothermal synthesis conditions were chosen based on optimum fluorescence quantum yield of the final product and these conditions are: citric acid (6.5 mmol) and ethylenediamine (12 mmol) were dissolved in 30 mL of water in a Teflon liner. The Teflon liner was placed in a stainless-steel autoclave and held at 200 °C for 5 hours.

After the autoclave was cooled to room temperature, the reaction products were subjected to dialysis with cellulose dialysis tubing of different pore size (1, 14 and 25 kDa molecular weight cut-off, MWCO) for one week, changing the water containing the dialysate outside the dialysis bag every day. In case of dialysis with a 1 kDa MWCO membrane for one week, the dry mass content of the retained material is approximately 20 mg, resulting in a mass yield of 1%. Although this is a low yield, when characterizing this retained material, it is observed by the different structural and photophysical characterization techniques that there are still a large number of small molecules masking the graphitic structures. On the other hand, in the case of dialysis with 25 kDa MWCO membranes for the same time span, the retained material was insufficient to be fully characterized. Finally, dialysis with 14 kDa MWCO membrane allowed to obtain sufficient retained material (labeled in the following as B-CNDs) for analysis (5 mg, mass yield 0.25%), but minimizing as much as possible by dialysis the interference of dissolved molecular and oligomeric compounds. Alternatively, size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) was performed to separate fractions.

Morphological and structural characterization of the B-CNDs

The retentate material from the dialysis was separated by UPLC into thirteen fractions within 12 min, where it should be evident that only small molecules can be detected by this technique, not the CNDs themselves. On the other hand, the dialyzed material revealed a very complex mixture with more than 40 kinds of chemical species, but, surprisingly, even after prolonged dialysis, small molecules are still observed in the B-CNDs and are the same as those found in the dialysate (Fig. 1). The high-accuracy mass spectra of the most representative fractions of the B-CNDs sample are

Fig. 1 Gradient elution of B-CNDs (left-hand side) and dialyzed material (right-hand side). The chromatograms are monitored with ESI-Q-TOF MS/MS and only the mass spectra of the main molecules observed in the B-CNDs are shown. These main molecules are identical to those found in the dialysate.

displayed in Fig. 1. Fraction 10 is the main one and contains a compound with a mass of 181.0610, which corresponds to a chemical species with formula $C_8H_9N_2O_3$ resulting from the four-fold dehydrated product of the union of a molecule of citric acid and a molecule of ethylenediamine. This molecule has already been reported as imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine-7-carboxylic acid, 1,2,3,5-tetrahydro-5-oxo, IPCA.²³ The next most relevant fraction is fraction 8, which reveals a compound with mass of 223.1187, corresponding to a chemical formula $C_{10}H_{15}N_4O_2$, a molecule arising from the union of a molecule of citric acid, two molecules of ethylenediamine and subsequent five-fold dehydration. This molecule (*N*-(2-aminoethyl)-5-oxo-1,2,3,5-tetrahydroimidazol[1,2-a]pyridine-7-carboxamide, IPCA-EDA) is another fluorescent molecule found in the B-CNDs. Other relevant fractions are fractions 3, 4, 5, 7 and 9, which reveal chemical species with formulae $C_8H_{13}N_2O_5$, $C_7H_{13}N_2O_3$, $C_{10}H_{17}N_4O_3$, $C_{10}H_{19}N_4O_4$, and $C_8H_{15}N_2O_6$, respectively. All these molecular formulae correspond to molecules that occur in the scheme of synthesis of IPCA and IPCA-EDA, but these are not yet sufficiently conjugated to act as molecular fluorophores (compare Scheme S1 of the ESI†). Also noteworthy are the fractions 6 and 13 which reveal the presence of chemical species with the formulae $C_{13}H_{21}N_2O_{10}$ and $C_{13}H_{13}N_2O_6$. Those molecules result from the union of a molecule of ethylenediamine and two molecules of citric

acid, once decarboxylated and two or six times dehydrated, respectively. The molecule with the highest molecular weight 379.1248 is found in fraction 11 and corresponds to a molecular formula of $C_{16}H_{19}N_4O_7$. It derives from the union of two molecules of citric acid and two molecules of ethylenediamine after seven-fold dehydration. The mass spectra of fractions 1, 2 and 12 (Fig. S1, ESI†) arise from the eluent and can be seen in the blank (Fig. S2, ESI†). In addition, the mass spectra of some of the minority fractions, besides containing peaks corresponding to molecular products of the reaction, also show peaks coming from the eluent or instrument noise. All the identified molecules are much smaller than the pore size of dialysis tubes, the only possible explanation for finding them in the retentate is that they are bound through non-covalent forces to the graphitic cores and partially released after the dialysis.

HR-TEM images could only be obtained on single layer graphene TEM supports. Graphene offers a support that is more conductive and also much thinner than the average amorphous carbon supports, and although it is a crystalline support, its contribution to signal formation is relatively low (Fig. S3, ESI†). These images show that the collected B-CNDs are fairly monodisperse and have a uniform size of about 3 nm (Fig. 2). AFM images of the B-CNDs deposited on a mica substrate reveal heights of also approximately 3 nm, suggesting that the B-CNDs have a near spherical shape and typically consist of 8–9 graphene layers (Fig. S4, ESI†). HR-TEM measurements of B-CNDs revealed lattice spacings of 0.12, 0.16, 0.21 and 0.32 nm, respectively, which is consistent with the (110), (004), (100) and (002) diffraction planes of sp^2 graphitic carbon and another lattice spacing of 0.26 nm, which cannot be assigned to graphitic carbon (Fig. 2).

The HR-TEM images do not show the molecular products identified by mass spectrometry, but the 0.26 nm lattice spacings observed in these images that cannot be associated with graphitic structures could be due to aggregates of these molecular products. To solve this conflict, we resort to grazing incidence wide angle X-ray scattering (GI-WAXS). The GI-WAXS spectrum of the B-CNDs at room temperature shows many signals corresponding to lattice spacings of 0.36, 0.32, 0.30, 0.22, 0.21, 0.18, 0.17 nm, respectively, but upon heating to 200 °C in air most of the signals disappear or are noticeably

Fig. 3 2D GI-WAXS spectra and radially integrated scattered intensity obtained at 25 and 200 °C of B-CNDs (left) and dialyzed material (right). Numbers mark lattice spacings of the B-CNDs.

reduced, leaving only two dominant signals corresponding to 0.30 and 0.21 nm (Fig. 3). These results indicate that the majority of the signals observed in the GIWAXS spectrum of B-CNDs at room temperature correspond to molecular products that degrade at a high temperature, leaving only the signals corresponding to the graphitic structures (0.30 and 0.21 nm, associated with the (002) and (100) diffraction planes of the sp^2 graphitic carbon, respectively), which are stable up to at least 200 °C in air. The same experiments were performed also for the dialyzed material, resulting in a GIWAXS spectrum at 200 °C showing no remarkable signal. All other peaks observed at room temperature for the dialysate therefore likely arise from molecular aggregates which are destroyed at 200 °C (Fig. 3).

Whereas the AFM and HR-TEM measurements reveal monodisperse graphitic cores of about 3 nm in diameter on a dry surface, dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements are able to produce the hydrodynamic size distribution in aqueous suspension. DLS in Milli-Q^s water at a pH of 7.4 of the B-CNDs (Fig. S5, ESI†) reveal two main populations, one of them with an average size of 42 ± 2 nm (which represents 10% in intensity, 54% in volume and 97% in number) and the other population with an average size of 133 ± 9 nm (which represents 90% in intensity, 46% in volume and 3% in number). This shows that in aqueous suspension the graphitic cores, despite some solubility thanks to the presence of functional groups or molecular products on their surface, tend to form large aggregates.

The results presented above were complemented by micro-SERS experiments which are able to reveal the chemical identity of the products (Fig. 4). These spectra are locally strongly enhanced in “hot spots” due to the electromagnetic fields of the nano-roughened gold surface. SERS spectra of the B-CNDs exhibit the well-known D and G bands (characteristics of graphitic structures) with a relatively weak, but non-negligible influence of the bands of functional groups of the molecular compounds. SERS spectra of the dialysate, on the other hand, show a series of much narrower Raman lines. A calculation of the Raman spectra of the major fraction of the molecular products, corresponding to the molecule IPCA, by density

Fig. 2 Representative HR-TEM images and fast Fourier transform (FFT) diffractions patterns of B-CNDs.

Fig. 4 Surface-enhanced micro-Raman spectra (SERS) of B-CNDs and dialyzed material on nano-rough gold surface and calculated Raman spectrum of IPCA ($\lambda_{exc} = 633 \text{ nm}$).

functional theory (marked in blue in Fig. 4) describes in fact the majority of the Raman lines of the dialysate. Comparing the calculated and experimentally observed intensities it must be kept in mind that SERS intensities often deviate considerably from conventional Raman spectra.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) enables the elucidation of the functional groups on the surface of B-CNDs. The FTIR spectra (Fig. S6, ESI[†]) of the B-CNDs are found to differ from those of the dialysate mainly in a significantly higher intensity of the vibration bands corresponding to the alkoxy C–O stretch and vibrations of the methyl group. Those are therefore ascribed to surface functional groups of the graphitic cores, whereas the otherwise almost identical FTIR spectra of B-CNDs and the dialysate, respectively, prove that molecular fractions are bound to the B-CNDs, considering also that graphitic cores without functional groups cannot produce any signals in the IR spectrum.

XPS spectroscopy is employed to complement the results of FTIR spectroscopy. Comparing the XPS spectra obtained from the dialyzed material and the B-CNDs, respectively (Fig. S7, ESI[†]), a decrease in signal intensity due to the presence of nitrogen and an increase in signal intensity due to the presence of oxygen is observed for B-CNDs, relative to the dialysate. This higher oxygen content again evidences the presence of functional groups such as OH or COOH on the surface of the graphitic cores. On the other hand, the enhanced presence of CQC bonds in the fitted spectra of the B-CNDs relative to the signals ascribed to C–H and CQO bonds, when compared to the dialysate, is in accordance with expectation for the graphitic cores.

Photophysical characterization of the B-CNDs

The fluorescence quantum yields differ drastically for the dialysate (84%) and the B-CNDs (0.79%), a result relevant for the interpretation of the outcome of the fluorescence correlation experiments to be discussed below. It was observed, however, that the initially almost colorless aqueous solutions of the dialyzed material gradually changed under daylight, at

Fig. 5 Photophysical characterization of dialyzed material and B-CNDs in H₂O. (a) Evolution of the material dialyzed in the dark under ambient illumination. Normalized emission–excitation maps, on a logarithmic intensity scale, of (b) dialyzed material collected after 5 hours of dialysis in the dark, (c) B-CNDs immediately after dialysis during one week in the dark, (d) dialyzed material after additional 14 days under ambient illumination and (e) B-CNDs after additional 14 days under ambient illumination, respectively, (f) UV-Vis absorption spectra of dialyzed material after dialysis in the dark (black) and after dialysis under ambient light (red) and B-CNDs dialyzed in the dark (green) and dialyzed under ambient light (blue), and (g) fluorescence decays ($\lambda_{exc} = 405 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{det} = 615 \text{ nm}$) of the material outside of the dialysis bag (dialysate), dialyzed without (black) and with (red) exposure to ambient light and B-CNDs dialyzed in the dark (green) and exposed to ambient light (blue).

room temperature and in the presence of atmospheric oxygen to maroon, then orange and finally becoming practically colorless again (Fig. 5a). More quantitatively, the evolution of dialyzed material under ambient illumination was monitored through emission–excitation maps and UV-Vis absorption. Fig. 5b–e displays the normalized emission–excitation maps, on a logarithmic scale, of dialyzed material collected after 5 hours of dialysis in the dark, B-CNDs after 1 week of dialysis in the dark, dialyzed material after 14 days under ambient illumination and B-CNDs after 14 days under ambient illumination, respectively. The main features in the maps of Fig. 5b and c, respectively, are very similar, which suggests that the same fluorophores are responsible for the emission of the retentate (B-CNDs) and the dialysate. As shown previously²³ and confirmed above the large majority of those fluorophores

corresponds to IPCA. Small differences in the shapes of the main feature in Fig. 5b and c can be ascribed to the modification of the spectra of the fluorophores due to their binding to the graphitic cores. In both, the dialysate and the retentate the formation of a satellite is observed after illumination (Fig. 5d and e, respectively). In the case of the dialysate the satellite is centered at 538/450 nm in emission/excitation, respectively. At the same time the intensity of the main emission centered at 440 nm is decreasing. In the case of the retentate a shoulder appears centered at 496/418 nm in emission/excitation, respectively. Both satellites are weakly present already in the maps of Fig. 5b and c, but, in particular in the case of the retentate, their shape is similar to the one observed after 14 days of illumination, such that their appearance must be ascribed to the dose of light received, in particular in the ultraviolet region of the spectrum, during acquisition of the maps. The obvious conclusion is that there are photoreactions in both the dialysate and the retentate, but they result in photoproducts with red-shifted, but somewhat different excitation and emission spectra. Emission spectra dependent on the excitation wavelength were extracted from the maps (see Fig. S8, ESI†). In both cases the emission spectra depend on the excitation wavelength as already evident from the maps, but in the case of the dialysate the emission is bimodal, whereas for the B-CNDs the spectra shift more gradually, most likely due to the inhomogeneity of the surroundings of the fluorophores bound to the graphitic cores. Interestingly, there is also a dark reaction as evidenced by differential emission/excitation maps of material kept in the dark (Fig. S9, ESI†). This dark reaction appears to be different for the dialysate and the retentate.

Fig. 5f shows the ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) absorption spectra of dialyzed material with and without exposure to ambient light and B-CNDs dialyzed with and without ambient light. Aqueous suspensions of B-CNDs dialyzed without light show an absorption spectrum virtually identical to the starting dialysate material, which demonstrates that the absorption of the B-CNDs is completely dominated by the small molecules produced in the synthesis. B-CNDs dialyzed under ambient light, on the other hand, show an absorption spectrum more similar to that of the dialysate material after exposure to light. This implies again that it is the photoproducts which cause the difference in the properties of the retentate and dialysate when the dialysis is carried out under ambient illumination. The monotonic development of the UV-VIS spectra of the dialysate under ambient illumination is demonstrated in Fig. S10 (ESI†). The absorption maximum at 240 nm of the pristine material was found to decrease progressively until it becomes a shoulder, the minimum of absorption found at 290 nm and the absorption tail that extends to the red region of the visible spectrum suffer a hyperchromic effect, and finally the maximum absorption found at 350 nm suffer a slight bathochromic shift that positions the maximum absorption at 340 nm.

The fluorescence of the material outside of the dialysis bag (dialysate), containing the molecular by-products, and extracted after 5 h of dialysis in the dark, exhibits a biexponential PL decay with time constants of 15.6 ns (intensity-weighted

amplitude 98%) and 3.6 ns (amplitude 2%), which possibly corresponds to two different molecular fluorophores, such as IPCA and IPCA-EDA. (Fig. 5g, black line). The fluorescence decay of the same dialysate after exposure to ambient light for 14 days can be fitted to a tetraexponential function with time constants of 15.4, 3.7, 0.6 and 0.27 ns with intensity-weighted amplitudes of 38%, 46%, 19% and 7%, respectively (Fig. 5g, red line). The fluorescence of B-CNDs dialyzed in the dark, on the other hand, exhibit decays that are fitted with a tetraexponential function with time constants of 12.0, 4.7, 1.5 and 0.29 ns with intensity-weighted amplitudes of 27%, 41%, 26% and 6%, respectively (Fig. 5g, green line), whereas the fluorescence decays of B-CNDs dialyzed under ambient light are fitted to a tetraexponential function with time constants of 13.3, 4.0, 0.7 and 31 ns with intensity-weighted amplitudes of 48%, 36%, 9% and 7%, respectively (Fig. 5g, blue line). Because the fluorescence decays of B-CNDs dialyzed in the dark and of the dialysate not exposed to ambient light on the one hand and of B-CNDs dialyzed in ambient light and of the dialysate exposed to light on the other hand are quite similar to each other, we can conclude that it is the creation of the photoproduct that causes most of the difference in the decay dynamics of B-CNDs and the dialysate.

An alternative method to separate fractions of the product of solvothermal synthesis is size-exclusion chromatography, where fractions of larger size appear first at the exit of the chromatography column. Fig. S11 (ESI†) shows excitation–emission maps of the principal fractions obtained. The map of the first fraction is very similar to the map of the retentate from dialysis (Fig. 5c), whereas the map of the next fraction is dramatically different. The map of the final fraction resembles the photoproduct of Fig. 5d. We therefore conclude that SEC appears to be able to separate two different fluorescent fractions plus the photoproduct.

In view of possible applications of the B-CNDs we also incorporated them into the water-soluble polymers polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP). Fig. S12 (ESI†) exhibits the emission–excitation maps of films produced from these doped polymers. Incorporation of the B-CNDs into the polymers obviously induces large inhomogeneous red shifts of the maps demonstrating a strong interaction of the B-CNDs with the polymeric substrate. The same strongly inhomogeneous interactions are also observed when the polymer is doped with the dialysate (results not shown here).

Fluorescence correlation spectroscopy (FCS) of the B-CNDs was also performed and indicates that the emission properties of B-CNDs are strongly dominated neither by the graphitic cores nor by molecular species linked to them, but rather by free molecules released by them. Fig. S13 (ESI†) shows the normalized FCS curves of the standards used (Atto-488 and Alexa-405), B-CNDs and the dialysate material. A fit of the correlations of B-CNDs reveals a hydrodynamic radius of (0.98 ± 0.08) nm and (0.48 ± 0.04) nm for excitation wavelengths of 405 and 488 nm, respectively, and the dialysate material shows a hydrodynamic radius of (1.1 ± 0.1) nm, and (0.45 ± 0.02) nm for excitation wavelengths of 405 and 488 nm,

respectively. This difference in the hydrodynamic radius observed for excitation wavelengths of 405 and 488 nm can be justified by the presence of different molecular fluorophores such as IPCA and IPCA-EDA, or the photoproducts studied, but in any case, the unexpectedly small hydrodynamic radii show that the emission of the retentate when excited in the 405–480 nm range is dominated by free molecular entities and not by the graphitic cores. This is in agreement with the low QY observed for the retentate. It may be of interest to note that no phosphorescence was observed in the case of the B-CNDs even after cooling to 1.5 K indicating a very low intersystem crossing yield and/or low phosphorescence quantum yield.

The capacity of B-CNDs and dialyzed material, respectively, to photosensitize $^1\text{O}_2$ was assessed in D_2O by time-resolved detection of the near-infrared $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence at 1275 nm. The luminescence observed is assigned to $^1\text{O}_2$ because the transient is completely quenched in presence of sodium azide (NaN_3 , a well-known $^1\text{O}_2$ quencher; 25 mM). As shown in Fig. 6, B-CNDs indeed generate $^1\text{O}_2$ with quantum yield $F_D = 0.42$, but the dialyzed material does not have this capacity. It is noteworthy that the lifetime of the singlet oxygen in D_2O should be 64 ms, as observed for flavin mononucleotide (reference photosensitizer), but in the presence of the CNDs this time is shortened to 10 ms, which implies that the B-CNDs also quench $^1\text{O}_2$.

In order to evaluate if the quenching of singlet oxygen is related to the molecular products, an experiment was made using phenalene-1-one as singlet oxygen photosensitizer and 1,3-diphenylisobenzofuran as singlet oxygen trap whose bleaching can be monitored by its absorbance at 410 nm and a UV light-emitting diode was used as the light source ($\lambda_c = 365$ nm) (Fig. S14, ESI†). The illumination intensity at the sample was set to the same value in these experiments (12.9 W cm^{-2}).

As can be seen in Fig. S15 (ESI†), the absorption of 1,3-diphenylisobenzofuran decreases in the presence of phenalene-1-one under visible light with a constant of 0.014 min^{-1} and

Fig. 6 Singlet oxygen phosphorescence kinetics at 1275 nm in D_2O solutions of B-CNDs (blue), dialyzed material (green), reference photosensitizers (red) and B-CNDs in presence of NaN_3 (grey) ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 473$ nm).

when a small amount of the dialyzed material solution is added (the concentration of dialyzed material was adjusted to an absorbance value 10 times lower than that of phenalene-1-one at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 365$ nm) the absorption of 1,3-diphenylisobenzofuran decreases with a time constant of 0.002 min^{-1} , 7 times smaller than in the absence of the dialysate. This result shows that the dialysate indeed acts as a singlet oxygen deactivator, which limits the lifetime of singlet oxygen generated by B-CNDs. This result, of course, should also apply to the same molecular products attached to the surface of the B-CNDs.

Synthetic procedures of R-CNDs

In order to compare some of the findings discussed above with results obtained on a different kind of CNDs we have prepared red-emitting CNDs.^{33–35} 2.8 mmol of *p*-phenylenediamine (*p*-PDA) was first dissolved in 30 mL absolute ethanol and then the solution was transferred to a Teflon liner and the latter to a stainless-steel autoclave. After heating at 180 °C in an oven for 12 h and allowing to cool down to room temperature, a dark-red suspension was obtained. The crude products were subjected to dialysis with a membrane MWCO of 14 kDa against an aqueous ethanol solution (15% v/v) for one week. After dialysis, approximately 12 mg R-CNDs were obtained, representing a 4% yield by mass.

Morphological and structural characterization of the R-CNDs

By using UPLC separation, the R-CNDs were well separated into approximately 40 fractions in less than 12 min. For its part, the dialyzed material revealed a very similar and complex mixture with more than 50 kinds of chemical species, but the most relevant molecules are the same as the one observed in the R-CNDs (Fig. 7). The high-accuracy MS analyses mass and mass/mass spectra of the most representative fractions of the R-CNDs sample are also displayed in Fig. 7.

The first fraction (approx. 3% of separated material) contains a compound with a mass of 321.1818, which revealed a chemical species with formula $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6$ resulting from the union of three molecules of *p*-phenylenediamine. To know which structural isomer is formed by the union of three *p*-phenylenediamine molecules and gives rise to the chemical species $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6$ we use tandem mass spectrometry (Fig. S16, ESI†); this allows us to identify some molecular fragments of a single molecule (Tri-*p*PDA). The following fraction (approx. 48% of separated material) reveals a compound with a mass of 369.1819 corresponding to a chemical formula $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_6$. In this case the molecule arises from the union of four molecules of *p*-phenylenediamine and two losses of HCN (tetra-*p*PDA), which can result in more than 20 different structural isomers practically indistinguishable by mass spectrometry (two of which are shown in Fig. 7). The third fraction (approx. 12% of separated materials) reveals a compound with mass of 211.0976 corresponding to a chemical formula $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4$, in this case the molecule arises from the union of two molecules of *p*-phenylenediamine and an additional dehydrogenation (Bi-*p*PDA-1). The fourth fraction (approx. 6% of separated

Fig. 7 Gradient elution of R-CNDs (left) and dialyzed material (right). The chromatograms are monitored with ESI-Q-TOF MS/MS and the mass spectra of the main molecules observed in the R-CNDs are reproduced, which are the same as those identified in the dialysate.

materials) reveals a compound with mass of 419.1729 corresponding to a chemical formula $C_{24}H_{19}N_8$ that arises from the union of four molecules of *p*-phenylenediamine, but the tandem mass spectrometry does not allow us to distinguish between two possible structural isomers (tetra-*p*-PDA). The tenth fraction (approx. 26% of separated material) reveals a compound with a mass of 213.1130 corresponding to a chemical formula $C_{12}H_{13}N_4$. In this case the molecule arises from the union of two molecules of *p*-phenylenediamine (Bi-*p*PDA). All these molecules identified by UPLC-MS appear in the synthetic Scheme S2 of the ESI.† It should be noted that the fractions separated by UPLC for both the dialysate material and the R-CNDs that elute between 7 and 8 min and at 10 min, at least in part derive from the eluent and can also be seen in the blank (Fig. S17, ESI†).

STEM images could only be obtained on TEM graphene support films, these images show that the R-CNDs contain two types of particles: particles of an average size of 15.5 nm that are polycrystalline or amorphous and crystalline particles of an average size of 2.9 nm with a lattice spacing of 0.22 nm which coincides with the diffraction plane (100) of graphitic carbon sp^2 (Fig. 8). Although on the surface we could see monodisperse graphitic cores of about 3 nm in size, we were also interested in knowing the hydrodynamic size. For this purpose, we carried out dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements in Milli-Q[®] water at a pH of 7.4 of the R-CNDs (Fig. S18, ESI†). It can be observed that the R-CNDs show a very broad distribution of hydrodynamic diameters with a mean diameter of (260 ± 80) nm. This indicates that, similar to the B-CNDs, R-CNDs have a strong tendency to form aggregates of various sizes.

Fig. 8 Representative STEM images of R-CNDs. The images are characterized by small crystalline particles of average size 2.9 nm and larger polycrystalline or amorphous particles of average size 15.5 nm. Images (a and d) are representative for both fractions, respectively. Images (b and e) show typical examples of the two kinds of particles and, in the case of the small crystalline particles, the fast Fourier transform of the image. The size distributions of the two fractions, as obtained from images covering a larger area, are reproduced in figures (c and f).

Surface-enhanced micro-Raman spectroscopy of the R-CNDs indicates the coexistence of the molecules identified by mass spectrometry and the graphitic cores observed by HR-TEM. Raman spectra of the R-CNDs show D and G bands (characteristics of the graphitic structures). On the other hand, the Raman spectra of the dialyzed material show narrower Raman bands characteristic of molecular products (Fig. 9).

The functional groups on the surface of R-CNDs are identified by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). The corresponding spectra (Fig. S19, ESI†) are very similar for the dialysate and the R-CNDs confirming that the FTIR spectrum of the R-CNDs essentially reveals the molecular products. Three FTIR bands of the R-CNDs that are not observed in the dialysate occur at 649, 835 and 1505 cm^{-1} , respectively, and are marked in blue in Fig. S19 (ESI†), whereas a single band that is observed in the dialysate, but not in the R-CNDs, is marked in red. The former three bands should be ascribed to functional groups of the graphitic cores of the R-CNDs, in particular to aromatic azo groups (1505 cm^{-1}), vinyl ether groups (835 cm^{-1}) and saturated aliphatic nitro compounds (649 cm^{-1}).

Fig. 9 Surface-enhanced micro-Raman spectra (SERS) of R-CNDs, dialyzed material on nano-rough gold surface ($I_{\text{exc}} = 633 \text{ nm}$).

Photophysical characterization of the R-CNDs

The ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) absorption spectra of R-CNDs, the dialyzed material and *p*-phenylenediamine are shown in Fig. 10C. A solution of *p*-phenylenediamine in EtOH is characterized by two intense absorption peaks around 243 and 309 nm. The dialyzed material approximately maintains one of the absorption maxima observed in the synthesis precursor, now at 248 nm, suggesting that it contains unreacted *p*-phenylenediamine. In addition, the UV-Vis absorption spectrum of the dialyzed material shows another absorption maximum at 278 nm and a wide absorption band ranging from 370 to 740 nm with a maximum at 489 nm. On the other hand, R-CNDs, similar to the dialyzed material, show a maximum absorption at 279 nm and a wide absorption band ranging from 388 to 740 nm with a maximum absorption at 497 nm. That is,

Fig. 10 Photophysical characterization of dialyzed material and R-CNDs in EtOH, (A and B) normalized emission-excitation maps of dialyzed material and R-CNDs, respectively, on a linear intensity scale, (C) UV-Vis absorption spectra of dialyzed material, R-CNDs and *p*-phenylenediamine (*p*-PDA) and (D) time resolved fluorescence (TRF) decays ($I_{\text{exc}} = 405 \text{ nm}$, $I_{\text{det}} = 615 \text{ nm}$) of R-CNDs (black) and dialysate (red), respectively.

R-CNDs exhibit a UV-Vis absorption spectrum similar to that of the dialyzed material, without the absorption corresponding to the presence of unreacted *p*-phenylenediamine.

The emission-excitation map of dialyzed material (Fig. 10A) reveals an emission maximum centered at 394 nm for excitation wavelengths between 300 and 350 nm corresponding to the unreacted *p*-phenylenediamine, and two other emission maxima centered at 594 nm for excitation wavelengths between 335 and 375 nm as well as between 430 and 580 nm. The emission-excitation map of R-CNDs (Fig. 10B), on the other hand, reveals a weak emission centered at 394 nm, corresponding to the *p*-phenylenediamine remaining unreacted in the R-CNDs, but shows the other two emission maxima in a similar way as the dialyzed material. In this case the emission is almost 50 nm wider and is centered at 595 nm for excitation wavelengths between 360 and 395 nm and between 400 and 590 nm. Similar to the B-CNDs, this seems to indicate that the emission of the R-CNDs is related to fluorophores attached to the graphitic cores during dialysis and constantly released into the liquid thereafter. In contrast to the B-CNDs, however, we did not observe any photoproducts of those fluorophores. The PL QYs determined were 28% and 1.6% for the dialyzed material and R-CNDs, respectively. For individual spectra extracted from the maps of Fig. 10a, b and see Fig. S20 (ESI†).

The fluorescence of the dialyzed material exhibits a triexponential decay with time constants of 4.5, 2.3 and 0.31 ns with intensity-weighted amplitudes of 61%, 22% and 17%, respectively, which likely corresponds to different molecular fluorophores. For R-CNDs the fluorescence decays were fitted with a triexponential function with time constants of 7.0, 1.9 and 0.48 ns with amplitudes of 45%, 25% and 30%, respectively (Fig. 10D). As with the B-CNDs, the PL decay times observed for R-CNDs are similar to those of the dialyzed material but show a faster decay at short times, which should be attributed to quenching by the graphitic cores to which the molecules are attached in the case of the R-CNDs. It may be of interest in this context to note that a recent study,³⁶ of red-emitting CNDs produced from citric acid and urea also came to the conclusion, but based on a method of orthogonal solvents, that the absorption and emission of the reaction product were produced by small conjugated molecules, without identifying the latter, however, and without investigating the graphitic cores produced in the synthesis.

Conclusions

Hydrothermal or, in general, solvothermal treatments have become the most common procedure for production of CNDs due to their environmental friendliness, simplicity and versatility, generating CNDs from the condensation of carbonaceous blocks and the crystallization of the graphitic cores induced by high temperature and/or pressure. We have collected rather convincing evidence, however, that the UV-Vis, PL and PL excitation spectra and PL decays of the products of solvothermal synthesis of the B-CNDs, as well as the R-CNDs studied

here are dominated by small molecules, some of which we have identified through UPLC-ESI-Q-TOF-MS/MS, and, in the case of the B-CNDs, their photoproducts. Comparison and careful analysis of the optical and structural properties of the low molecular weight products that are dialyzed and of the CNDs proves that the molecular fluorophores observed in the dialysate still appear in the retentate, even after prolonged dialysis, suggesting that those compounds are attached to the graphitic cores and/or amorphous aggregates and constantly being released into the liquid surrounding. This may indeed confer varied and chemically controllable functionalities and photophysical properties useful for applications to the CNDs. It demonstrates, however, that even extended dialysis cannot guarantee the absence of small conjugated fluorophores. No photophysical characteristics of sp^2 domains in the graphitic cores have been identified in the present work, contrary to previous assignments and contrary to the concept of “carbon quantum dots”, which, in analogy to semiconductor quantum dots, suggests optical properties dominated by coherent size effects. In the case of our B-CNDs photoproducts, previously ignored, have been shown in the present study to dominate the photophysical properties of the retentate, when the dialysis is not carried out in the dark, and readily explain photophysical differences between dialysate and retentate, which were previously ascribed to the sp^2 domains of the graphitic cores. A recent study³⁷ on the formation of CNDs employing small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) and optical spectroscopy suggests a core-shell structure of their CNDs with aromatic groups within the core of the CNDs. This model may also be applicable to the CNDs investigated here, explaining the escape of the aromatic molecules from the CNDs on an extended time scale, but implying that the aromatic molecules are not covalently bound to the cores.

At the moderate temperatures employed by us in the solvothermal synthesis graphitic cores, on the other hand, are produced in a very low yield, but are identified by HR-TEM, GIWAXS and SERS. HR-TEM analysis reveals the presence of amorphous aggregates, presumably consisting of non-conjugated molecules, which we detected and partially identified *via* UPLC-ESI-Q-TOF-MS/MS, and non-conjugated polymers. In spite of the low yield of graphitic CNDs we have shown that the latter are almost exclusively responsible for the generation of singlet oxygen, which we partly ascribe to the low intersystem crossing yield of the fluorophores. The exact mechanism of formation of singlet oxygen at the graphitic cores, however, remains to be explored. It may also be worth noting that the B-CNDs were previously confirmed to be able to anchor nucleic acids,²⁰ in contrast to the dialysate material, constituting another example where the graphitic cores confer unique functionalities, in spite of the overwhelming presence of small molecules in the product of solvothermal synthesis.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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